

COAR NARRATIVE SERIES

Repositories Unlock the Potential of Multilingual Scholarship

Confederation of Open Access Repositories

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Multilingualism is a defining characteristic of a healthy, inclusive, and genuinely global research communications landscape. Publishing in local languages ensures that the public in different countries can access and benefit from the research they fund, while also reducing the structural disadvantage faced by researchers who do not work in English. The stakes extend beyond individual careers. As COAR (2023) has stated, following the Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism in Scholarly Communication (2019):

“The disqualification of local or national languages in academic publishing is the most important – and often forgotten – factor that prevents societies from using and taking advantage of the research done where they live.”

A system that only speaks one language cannot claim to represent global knowledge.

Repositories contain resources in many different languages

Repositories are well-positioned to advance the dissemination of multilingual research, precisely because they function as locally-governed nodes in a global network rather than as centralised platforms optimised for a single user base. Most repository interfaces can already be configured to operate in multiple languages, and in many countries, a significant proportion of deposited content is published in languages other than English. This is a structural advantage that international and commercial platforms cannot easily replicate because they are designed to maximise engagement and market reach and, therefore, are built around English as the default. Repositories, by contrast, reflect the linguistic reality of the communities they serve, making them not only a more equitable foundation for global scholarly communication but a more representative one.

Although English has long served as the de facto language of international scientific discourse, this dominance is increasingly being questioned. Governments in many regions are reassessing the role of local languages in research communication, driven by concerns about public access, cultural relevance, and the challenges imposed on non-English-speaking researchers. In recognition of this, Latin America has maintained its own community-governed publishing ecosystem for decades, with regional journals publishing predominantly in Spanish and Portuguese, a model that is now attracting broader interest. In China, for instance, after years of incentivising publication in Science Citation Index (SCI)-indexed international journals, the government has begun to reverse course, reducing reliance on "SCI-only" evaluation and promoting greater publication in Chinese and domestic journals (Owens, 2024; Yang & Huang, 2025). Similarly, the Canadian federal government has invested in strengthening the French language research ecosystem in response to evidence that francophone researchers face structural disadvantages within English-dominated publishing and evaluation systems (Canadian Heritage, 2023; Beth et al., 2024). In Europe, the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) has formed a working group on multilingualism and language biases, which has produced a draft proposal for language-aware research

assessment (CoARA WG on Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessment, 2025). These shifts reflect a growing recognition that a research communications system built almost exclusively around one language is neither equitable nor, in the long run, optimised for knowledge exchange.

Repositories are high on the list of infrastructures for sharing and preserving multilingual research outputs. Some of the most prominent examples illustrate the breadth of this role. HAL, France's national open repository, is used as an institutional repository by 98% of French universities and hosts over 1.5 million full-text documents, 27% of which are in French (CCSD, 2026). Japan's National Institute of Informatics (NII) operates a national repository hosting and aggregation service containing thousands of Japanese-language documents. Brazil's IBICT coordinates a nationwide repository network dedicated to collecting and preserving Portuguese-language research outputs across the country. Beyond these national cases, a 2024 study of the European repository landscape conducted by COAR (Shearer et al., 2023) found that repositories across the continent routinely maintain substantial collections in their national languages, suggesting that linguistic diversity is already a feature of repository infrastructure rather than an aspiration. Taken together, these examples demonstrate that repositories are active participants in sustaining the multilingual character of global scholarship.

Current discovery systems do not surface this multilingualism

Despite the fact that researchers around the world produce knowledge in hundreds of languages, this content is largely invisible to non-native speakers. When we go looking for that knowledge, the tools at our disposal behave as if only a handful of languages truly matter. And, although researchers and other information seekers may be able to read in only one or two languages, they still want to know about all the relevant research in their field, regardless of the language in which it is published. Yet discovery systems such as Google Scholar have a systemic bias in their algorithms against non-English content (Rovira et al., 2021), and other scholarly indexes simply exclude large portions of non-English publications in their services (Harzing, 2016), making non-English research outputs essentially invisible. At the same time, most discovery systems operate within linguistic boundaries: queries submitted in one language tend to return results primarily in that same language. This creates linguistic silos, where relevant research produced in other languages remains effectively invisible—not because it lacks relevance, but because systems are not designed to connect knowledge across languages.

The bias towards English content has also been baked into research evaluation systems in such a way that strongly incentivises researchers to publish in English. Because the major indexing and citation services largely ignore non-English content, researchers who wish to be recognised in assessment processes that rely on these indexes have little

choice but to publish in English. The Helsinki Initiative on Multilingualism in Scholarly Communication (2019) has warned that if funding systems continue to reward only English-language outputs, multilingual scholarly communication will not merely stagnate but be structurally eroded, a self-reinforcing cycle in which invisibility becomes irrelevance.

The structural biases have significant epistemic consequences. Konno et al. (2020) showed that omitting non-English-language studies from scientific reviews can significantly change their conclusions, and even reverse them. In terms of citations, Amano et al. (2023) found that non-English-language references account for about 65% of citations in national biodiversity reports. However, only 3.4% of the references appeared in global assessments by the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. When non-English literature is systematically excluded, the evidence base for policy, clinical practice, and community action is not just incomplete, it is also potentially misleading.

These structural imbalances are being further compounded by artificial intelligence. Large language models are predominantly trained on English-language corpora, and their performance degrades significantly in languages that are underrepresented in their training data (Bengio et al., 2026). Because these models learn from existing information environments that already overwhelmingly favour English, their outputs do not merely reflect historical linguistic hierarchies; they actively reinforce and extend them. As AI becomes more deeply embedded in how research is produced, discovered, and synthesised, the risk is that biases which were once the product of human decisions become encoded into systems that appear neutral, and are therefore harder to challenge.

Placing multilingualism at the centre of the global knowledge commons

The historical case for English as the default language of science was not without logic. A common medium of communication was genuinely useful, and English had emerged as the most widely shared option across research communities. But that rationale was always a practical compromise, and the technology now exists to overcome this issue. Large language models offer translation quality comparable to dedicated supervised systems, even for language pairs they were not explicitly trained on (Hendy et al., 2023). Multilingual embedding models create shared semantic spaces across languages, enabling search and retrieval based on meaning rather than keyword matching (Reimers & Gurevych, 2020; Matas, 2025). Knowledge graphs, meanwhile, can enable cross-cultural entity resolution, identifying the same concept, person, or institution regardless of how it is described in different languages. Taken together, these advances mean that content published in any language can, in principle, be discovered and

understood by someone searching in any other language. The language barrier that once made English dominance seem inevitable is now a problem with technical solutions.

A number of parallel efforts to improve multilingual discovery are also underway in specific domains. In Europe, for example, the OPERAS research infrastructure runs GoTriple, a discovery platform for the social sciences and humanities that facilitates access to resources in multiple languages from a variety of sources in several countries. And a conceptual model for semantic multilingual search, recently developed within the COAR community, proposes that meaning-based retrieval could operate as a complementary layer to the existing keyword search (Matas, 2025). Rather than matching exact words, this approach captures the underlying meaning of both documents and queries, enabling retrieval based on semantic similarity across languages. In this way, a query expressed in one language can surface relevant research produced in another, without requiring users to anticipate or translate keywords. The model proposes exposing this capability through the same interoperability mechanisms discussed above, allowing institutions to adopt the technology based on their resources. Though this approach remains at an exploratory stage, early proofs of concept have shown encouraging results, for example, with less dominant languages gaining greater visibility.

A global multilingual discovery system will require a coherent, distributed network of data providers across the world using shared standards and protocols that can be indexed at scale while preserving their local governance and linguistic diversity; systems that can connect queries and content across languages, rather than operating within a single linguistic context. Repositories are ideally placed to be part of this foundation, not only because of the content they hold, but because of the way they are designed: as interoperable, distributed systems capable of exposing structured metadata at scale. Unlike the major scholarly indexes, whose coverage is based mainly on publications in international journals and are heavily skewed toward English-language content, repositories exist in every part of the world, reflecting genuine geographic and linguistic diversity. A discovery system built on repositories would therefore produce a more complete picture of the multilingual global research environment than is currently available.

The technical prerequisites for such a system already exist within the global repository network. Repositories are built with interoperability as a core design principle: they adopt common standards and protocols (most notably OAI-PMH) that allow content to be exposed in consistent, machine-readable ways across different platforms and organisations. However, genuine multilingual discovery will require some additional practices to be adopted by repositories. In 2023, the COAR Task Force on Supporting Multilingualism and non-English Content in Repositories published 13 recommended practices for repositories for better exposing their content. While some progress has

been made in terms of uptake of these recommendations, many repositories have not yet adopted them fully and they have not been integrated into most repositories' curation workflows, exposing the need for more work to be done to begin to address this issue.

Advancing this vision at the speed and scale it requires will demand greater coordination and commitment in the repository community. By design, repositories are distributed and largely autonomous, coordinating through broad consensus-building rather than centralised governance. This includes not only the adoption of shared standards, but also greater alignment in metadata practices, multilingual description, and exposure of content for machine processing. However, these are not insurmountable problems but rather the kind of collective action challenges that the community has solved before, such as through widespread adoption of OAI-PMH and the COAR Next Generation Repository recommendations. In the coming months, COAR will undertake a number of activities to enhance community coordination through a potential pilot project and increase our efforts to promote good practices across the repository community that will enhance the value of multilingual content contained in the repository network.

Conclusion

The dominance of English in scholarly communications was never a principled design choice. It was a practical accommodation that hardened, over time, into an assumption so pervasive it became nearly invisible. The consequences of that assumption are now well documented: research produced in hundreds of languages goes undiscovered, evidence bases for policy and practice are systematically incomplete, and the researchers and communities whose knowledge is excluded bear costs that are rarely counted by those who benefit from the current system. As AI becomes more deeply embedded in how research is found and used, the risk is that these imbalances become computational, encoded into systems that appear objective and are therefore far harder to contest.

What has been missing is not the technology, the content, or even the technical standards. It is the recognition that multilingualism is not a niche concern but a necessary condition of the global knowledge commons. The good news is that the infrastructure needed to build something better already exists. Repositories, distributed across every region of the world and governed by the communities they serve, hold vast collections of multilingual research. They are built on interoperability standards that make indexing and crawling at scale technically feasible. And they are beginning to adopt the practices that a genuinely inclusive discovery system would require.

Repositories offer a credible path toward something genuinely different: a scholarly communication system that reflects much greater linguistic diversity, governed by the communities that produce it, and resilient enough to remain open regardless of whether

commercial or geopolitical pressures shift. Realising that potential will require coordinated standards and the collective will to treat multilingualism not as an add-on but as a founding principle. The case for acting is strong. The tools are available. What is needed now is to put them into action.

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